

Supplementary information for Simulating the international clade IIb mpox spread patterns in Asia, 2023 and onwards

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Material and methods

Model of international spread of mpox

We developed a stochastic meta-population SEIR model accounting for heterogeneous MSM sexual networks. We focused solely on the MSM populations in our model given the demonstrated predominance of this population group both empirically and theoretically¹⁻³ in the global mpox outbreak. To reflect the high heterogeneity in empirical data on sexual behaviours,³ the MSM population in each country/territory was subdivided into 50 groups of different sexual activity levels (i.e. the number of sexual partners per day). Each group was indexed by $k=1,2,\dots,50$ and is matched with one of the evenly spaced bins on a logarithmic scale between 1 and 10,000 partners per year. We allocated individuals to each group proportionally to the sexual partner distributions estimated from the reported 4-week (or 1-year for the sensitivity analysis) sexual partners in the Natsal data,^{3,4} and the rates of sexual partnerships per day for each group, r_k , was calculated as the mean given the probability density within each bin, scaled to the daily unit (Figure S1). Note that the highest sexual activity groups were not necessarily included in the modelled populations due to extremely low frequencies; e.g. the highest and second-highest sexual activity groups in the Natsal 4-week sexual partner distribution (corresponding to 9,041 and 7,522 annual partners, respectively) had frequencies of $\sim 10^{-8}$ and thus did not appear in the main analysis where the assumed MSM population sizes were at most $\sim 10^{-7}$.

Figure S1. Sexual activity groups for the mpox transmission model over MSM networks.

(A) Rate of sexual partnerships for each sexual activity group. (B&C) Distribution of sexual activity groups based on the number of (B) 4-week and (C) 1-year sexual partners reported in the Natsal data.

We described the transitions between compartments as a Markov process in daily time steps. We let the daily transitions follow binomial processes:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta^{S_{i,k,t} \rightarrow E_{i,k,t+1}} &\sim \text{Binom}(S_{i,k,t}, 1 - \exp(-\lambda_{i,k,t})), \\ \Delta^{E_{i,k,t} \rightarrow I_{i,k,t+1}} &\sim \text{Binom}(E_{i,k,t}, 1 - \exp(-\gamma_1)), \\ \Delta^{I_{i,k,t} \rightarrow R_{i,k,t+1}} &\sim \text{Binom}(I_{i,k,t}, 1 - \exp(-\gamma_2)), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where i represents the country/territory (here after denoted as country i for convenience) and k represents the sexual activity level. The reciprocals $1/\gamma_1$ and $1/\gamma_2$ correspond to the assumed latent period (3 days⁵) and infectious period (10 days⁶) of mpox, respectively. The force of infection for those with sexual activity level k in country i on day t , $\lambda_{i,k,t}$, was given as the product of the transmission coefficient β and the rate of sexual partnerships with infectious individuals per day. We modelled the risk of experiencing infectious sexual contacts for individuals residing in country i considering three different transmission pathways: local transmission in country i , transmission from local individuals in country j whilst outbound travels, and transmission from inbound travellers visiting from country j .

$$\lambda_{i,k,t} = \beta r_k \left(\theta_{i,t} + \sum_{j \neq i} m_{ij} \theta_{j,t} + \sum_{j \neq i} \eta_{ji,t} \right), \quad (2)$$

where the first term ($\beta r_k \theta_{i,t}$) represents the daily rate of local individuals with sexual activity level k being infected by a local infectious sexual partner in country i on day t , the second term represents the daily rate of travellers from country i getting infected outside of country i on day t , and the third term represents the daily rate of local individuals being infected by travellers visiting from outside of

country i on day t . Here, r_k represents the rate of sexual partnership for an individual with sexual activity level k , $\theta_{i,t}$ represents the risk of contacting infectious sexual partners in country i and $\eta_{ji,t}$ represents the risk of contacting infectious sexual partners in country i who are inbound travellers from country j . Assuming proportionate mixing, these risks were modelled as the proportion of infectious sexual contacts on day t ($C_{inf,i,t}$) among the overall sexual contacts ($C_{all,i,t}$) over the infectious period $1/\gamma_2$. A more assortative mixing as an alternative to this proportionate mixing assumption is included in our sensitivity analysis (Figure S11).

$$\theta_{i,t} = \frac{C_{inf,i,t}}{C_{all,i,t}}, \quad \eta_{ji,t} = \frac{m_{ji}C_{inf,j,t}}{C_{all,i,t}},$$

$$C_{inf,i,t} = \sum_k \max\left(0, \frac{r_k}{\gamma_2} - 1\right) I_{i,k,t}, \quad C_{all,i,t} = \sum_k \frac{r_k}{\gamma_2} P(k) N_{i,MSM}. \quad (3)$$

$N_{i,MSM}$ is the MSM population size in country i . When constructing $C_{inf,i,t}$, we subtracted one from the number of sexual partners that an infectious person is expected to have over the infectious period of $1/\gamma_2$. This is to reflect the concept of the excess degree,⁷ which assumes that the number of partners one can transmit to is the total number of partners except one who infected the person. For interpretability, we transformed β into the secondary attack risk (SAR), i.e. transmission risk per sexual partner: SAR = $1 - \exp(-\beta)$.

International mixing matrix m_{ij} represents the cross-sectional proportion of individuals from country i travelling in country j and is the product of two factors: the daily number of travellers per capita and the average duration of international travels, D_T , which we assumed to be 7 days.

$$m_{ij} = \frac{M_{ij}D_T}{365N_{i,tot}}, \quad (4)$$

where M_{ij} is the annual travel volume from country i to country j , while $N_{i,tot}$ is the total population size in country i . It is noted that we used the international travel volume in 2019, which was not affected by the COVID-19 restriction.

During the simulation of the stochastic meta-population model described in Equation (1), we also sampled the daily number of importations between countries and territories in a post-hoc manner. Specifically, we first sampled the total number of importations on day $t+1$ from any country/territory, $n_{i,imp}(t+1)$, among new infections $\sum_k \Delta^{S_{i,k,t} \rightarrow E_{i,k,t+1}}$.

$$n_{i,imp}(t+1) \sim Binom\left(\sum_k \Delta^{S_{i,k,t} \rightarrow E_{i,k,t+1}}, \frac{\sum_{j \neq i} m_{ij}\theta_{j,t} + \sum_{j \neq i} \eta_{ji,t}}{\theta_{i,t} + \sum_{j \neq i} m_{ij}\theta_{j,t} + \sum_{j \neq i} \eta_{ji,t}}\right). \quad (5)$$

Then, if $n_{i,imp}(t+1)$ is nonzero, the number of importations stratified by the source country j , $n_{i,imp,j}(t+1)$ was determined by multinomial sampling:

$$n_{i,imp,j}(t+1) \sim Multinomial\left(n_{i,imp}(t+1), \frac{m_{ij}\theta_{j,t} + \eta_{ji,t}}{\sum_{j \neq i} m_{ij}\theta_{j,t} + \sum_{j \neq i} \eta_{ji,t}}\right). \quad (6)$$

Model parameter specifications

We summarise the parameter values used in the present study in Table S1. We assumed that MSM account for 1% of the total population for convenience because the latest age-sex disaggregated population data was not available for some countries. For 23 Asian countries whose latest UN population data for 2020 or later is available,⁸ this 1% assumption would translate to 1.6% to 3.3% of adult males aged 15-64 (i.e. age group representative of mpox cases²). These figures roughly correspond to the WHO's nationally adequate estimates: a median of 1.63% with an interquartile range of 0.26% to 3.10%.⁹

Table S1. Parameter specification for the international spread model of mpox.

Parameter Description	Value	Reference
Latent period, $1/\mu_1$	3 days	5
Infectious period, $1/\mu_2$	10 days	6
Proportion of MSM population among total population in each country/territory	1%	Assumed ⁹
Parameters for the Weibull distribution representing the sexual partner distribution over 4 weeks ^a	$\sigma=0.16, \kappa=1.32$	4
Parameters for the Weibull distribution representing the sexual partner distribution over 1 year ^a	$\sigma=0.10, \kappa=0.77$	3
Transmission coefficient β	Results in Table S3 and Figure S4-S7	Estimated

^a Weibull distributions were parameterised by the shape parameter σ and the Pareto exponent $\kappa (= \sigma/\theta^\sigma$ where θ is the scale parameter) as defined in Endo et al.³

Model fitting using alive particle filter

We calibrated our stochastic SEIR model for Japan to the observed weekly incidence from 16th January to 26th June 2023 by medical attendance date to estimate the transmission coefficient β . Where the medical attendance date was missing, we imputed it from the reporting date, using the mean empirical delay from medical attendance to reporting within our data, which we estimated to be 9 days. We assumed that the effect of intervention or behaviour change was negligible during this period. We used a Bayesian data assimilation approach via the alive particle filter (APF), one of the approximate Bayesian computation (ABC) algorithms.^{10,11} This approach allowed us to obtain posterior samples of β alongside the corresponding trajectories of mpox incidence by sexual activity levels k in Japan.

Following McKinley et al.,¹⁰ we implemented the ABC pseudo-marginal Metropolis-Hastings (ABC-PMMH) algorithm in which the likelihood was approximated by the APF. For efficiency, we employed two types of early rejection, which are described in section 4 in McKinley et al.¹⁰ First, a proposal was rejected if the total number of simulations in the APF exceeded the pre-specified number, which we

set as 5,000 multiplied by the number of particles (300 in our case). Second, during each iteration of the ABC-PMMH, the simulation may be terminated part-way to reject the proposal based on the interim likelihood where possible.

For the implementation of ABC, we employed the following tolerance ϵ based on the observed weekly incidence (y_t). Let the function h_t be

$$h_t(\epsilon) = \sum_{i=-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \text{Poisson}(y_t | y_t + i), \quad (7)$$

and we defined ϵ as the smallest ϵ that satisfies $h_t(\epsilon) \geq \rho$, where ρ is a pre-specified threshold (set at 0.5 in our study). The absolute difference between the simulated weekly incidence (x_t) and y_t should be less than ϵ at every time point t for acceptance.

We ran the model simulation initiating with one mpox case in Japan (corresponding to the first reported case with a medical attendance date of 16th January 2023) within the APF. The sexual activity level k for this initial case, for each run, was sampled from the sexual degree distribution $P(k)$ weighted by the degree, which we assumed to be proportional to the risk of infection, as shown in Figure S1B&C:

$$f(k) = \frac{r_k P(k)}{\sum_{k'} r_{k'} P(k')}, \quad (8)$$

This distribution $f(k)$ corresponds to $f_{x_0}(\cdot | \theta)$ in Algorithm 1 in McKinley et al.¹⁰

We used a weakly-informative prior for β (a half-Cauchy distribution with a location parameter of 0 and a scale parameter of 2.5). We obtained 10,000 samples from a single chain of ABC-PMMH after discarding the first 2,000 samples as burn-in, which were then thinned to 1,000 samples to reduce auto-correlation. We ensured that the effective sample size was at least 200 and the R-hat value was less than 1.05 for all chains.¹² We ran the APF with the obtained posteriors of β to record the associated trajectories of mpox infections.

Simulating international spread

Our ABC-PMMH model fitting to incidence data in Japan yielded 1,000 samples of transmission coefficient β and associated trajectories of mpox infections (i.e. the number of individuals in the SEIR compartments stratified by sexual activity level k) in Japan until 26 June 2023. For consistency with the observed international spread in Asia, we further conditioned these samples of β and trajectories on the established importation in the Republic of Korea (South Korea) by the end of the fitting period (26 June 2023). We first simulated international spread in Asian countries and territories using our metapopulation SEIR model given the previously obtained (unconditional) samples of β and infection trajectories. That is, we ran the model with prespecified β and incidence in Japan to obtain 50,000 simulations (50 runs per unconditional sample) of mpox international trajectories over three years (which were long enough to observe the entire course of spread in considered countries and territories). We then limited these simulations to only those observing ≥ 10 mpox cases in South Korea by the end of the fitting period. We recorded the first importation between specific country/territory pairs in each simulation run to visualise the simulated probabilities of importations and their generational orders.

All the analysis was performed in Julia v1.8.3. Visualisation was done in Julia v1.8.3 and R v4.2.2. We used the R package {ggalluvial} v0.12.5 to draw the Alluvial diagram. The data and codes are deposited at https://github.com/toshiakiasakura/projection_of_mpox_in_Asia.

Supplementary results

Epidemic situation in Japan

In the earlier phase of the 2022 global mpox outbreak when Western countries were particularly affected, only sporadic cases were observed in most Asian countries and territories, including Japan. From 16th January 2023 onward, sustained local transmission was reported in Japan. Among those cases in 2023, three were known to have reported international travel history (Figure S2). Two visited Asia and one visited North and Central America.

Figure S2. The epidemic curve in Japan, 25 July 2022—26 June 2023.

Projected mpox incidence in Japan

We projected the international spread of mpox, and we visualised the projected mpox incidence with and without the condition that ≥ 10 cases were observed in South Korea during the fitting period and compared it with the mpox incidence in Japan since 2023¹³ (Figure S3).

Figure S3. Projected mpox incidence in Japan from posterior samples. (A) The simulated trajectories of mpox incidence from the posterior samples conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea. The shaded area represents the fitting period from 16th January to 26th June 2023. (B) The simulated trajectories of mpox incidence from unconditional posterior samples. (C) Observed mpox incidence in Japan from the beginning of 2023 to 15 November 2024 (i.e. week 98).

First mpox reporting dates and cumulative cases in Asian countries and territories

We collected the first date of the mpox report in 2023 in each Asian country/territory as of 3 February 2025 and the cumulative incidence of mpox as of 21 January 2025 from the Our World in Data (OWID) websites¹³ (Table S2). If we did not find a citable source on the first case report, we used the first reporting date as recorded in OWID.

Countries without any reported cases as of 31 December 2024 are not included in Table S2: 1 out of 6 in Eastern Asian countries and territories (Mongolia); 3 out of 11 South-eastern Asian countries (Brunei, Timor-Leste, and Myanmar); 3 out of 7 Southern Asian countries (Bangladesh, Bhutan, and Maldives); all the 4 Central Asian countries (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan); 4 out of 14 Western Asian countries (Syria, Kuwait, Azerbaijan and Armenia).

According to OWID data, the mpox outbreak size from 2023 to 2024 is 5,232 and the median of projected final outbreak size in Asian countries and territories is 231 (95% credible interval: 183, 971057). The number of countries and territories with any reported cases between 1st January 2023 and 31st December 2024 is 21 excluding Japan, and the median of the projected countries and territories experiencing importation is 4 (95% credible interval: 2, 41).

Table S2. Cumulative incidence for 2022, 2023 and 2024, and the first reporting date of mpox in Asian countries and territories since 2023 (data as of 3 February 2025).

UN Region	Country/territory	Cumulative incidence in 2022	Cumulative incidence in 2023	Cumulative incidence in 2024	First reporting date since 2023	Source for the first report since 2023
Eastern Asia	Japan	8	224	20	2023-01-19*	14,15
Eastern Asia	Hong Kong	1 ^a	53 ^a	14	2023-02-04*	16
Eastern Asia	Taiwan	4 ^a	355 ^a	93	2023-02-15*	17-19
Eastern Asia	Republic of Korea	4	151	17	2023-03-13*	20,21
Eastern Asia	China (mainland)	1 ^a	1713 ^a	524	2023-05-31*	22
South-eastern Asia	Singapore	19	31	17	2023-01-01 ~ 2023-01-07 ^b	23
South-eastern Asia	Thailand	12	673	180	2023-02-01	OWID ^c

South-eastern Asia	Philippines	4	5	47	2023-05-13	OWID ^c
South-eastern Asia	Vietnam	2	119	88	2023-07-11*	²⁴ OWID ^c
South-eastern Asia	Malaysia	0	9	1	2023-07-26	²⁵
South-eastern Asia	Laos	0	1	0	2023-09-08	²⁶
South-eastern Asia	Indonesia	1	72	15	2023-10-13	²⁷
South-eastern Asia	Cambodia	0	1	12	2023-12-13	²⁸
Southern Asia	India	20	7	6	2023-01-06	²⁹
Southern Asia	Sri Lanka	2	2	0	2023-06-07*	³⁰
Southern Asia	Nepal	0	1	0	2023-06-16	³¹
Southern Asia	Iran	1	0	0		
Western Asia	United Arab Emirates	16	9	5	2023-01-11	OWID ^c
Western Asia	Lebanon	24	3	1	2023-01-22	OWID ^c
Western Asia	Saudi Arabia	8	661	95	2023-02-25	³²
Western Asia	Bahrain	1	1	0	2023-04-16	OWID ^c

Western Asia	Oman	0	3	2	2023-10-12	OWID ^c
Western Asia	Jordan	1	0	1	2024-09-01	³³
Western Asia	Cyprus	5	0	0	2024-12-15	³⁴
Western Asia	Qatar	5	0	0		
Western Asia	Georgia	2	0	0		
Western Asia	Türkiye	12	0	0		

* Countries and territories with at least one known importation from other Asian countries and territories.

^a We collected data for Taiwan and Hong Kong from the following websites.^{16,17} For mainland China, we subtracted the cumulative incidence in overall China from those in Taiwan and Hong Kong.

^b Only the weekly incidence was available and we could not identify the exact reporting date.

^c We used the first reporting date since 2023 in OWID when we did not find a citable source on the first case report.

Sensitivity analysis 1: sexual partner distribution and infectious period

As part of the sensitivity analysis, we estimated the SARs using the same approach as the main analysis but with varying assumptions for the sexual partner distribution and infectious period for the sensitivity analysis (Table S3). Specifically, instead of the reported number of 4-week sexual partners from the Natsal data we used for the main analysis, we used the number of 1-year sexual partners as the reference for the partnership distribution over the infectious period of mpox. We used the parameter values for the Weibull distribution, $\sigma = 0.10$ and $\kappa = 0.77$, estimated in the previous study (Table S1).³ We also varied the assumed infectious period (7 days or 14 days, instead of 10 days in the main analysis). Figures S4–S7 show the trace plot and posterior distribution for each scenario.

Using the same approach as the main analysis, we projected the international spread of mpox for the additional three scenarios considered in our sensitivity analysis. We show the simulated importation probabilities, along with the distribution of final outbreak size (i.e. total cumulative case counts at the end of the simulation) in Asia and the number of countries and territories with at least one mpox case among the simulations (Figure S8). We also compared the simulated and observed first importation dates (Figure S9). To minimise stochastic fluctuations associated with rare importation events, for this analysis we increased the number of simulations to 10 times the main analysis (i.e. 500,000 simulations in total and 500 runs per unconditional sample).

Table S3. Estimated SARs for each sexual partner distribution and infectious period.

Scenario	Simulation pattern		Unconditional estimates from the ABC-PMMH algorithm		Conditional estimates		
	Sexual partner distribution	Infectious period	β (95% CrI.) ^a	SAR, % (95 CrI.)	Valid samples (/ 50,000)	β (95% CrI.)	SAR, % (95 CrI.)
1 (main analysis)	Natsal 4-week	10 days	1.08 (0.52, 2.31)	66.0 (40.5, 90.1)	626	1.27 (0.64, 2.65)	72.0 (47.2, 93.0)
2	Natsal 1-year	10 days	0.09 (0.05, 0.18)	8.4 (4.6, 16.1)	856	0.10 (0.05, 0.22)	9.7 (5.1, 19.9)
3	Natsal 4-week	7 days	1.45 (0.66, 3.04)	76.6 (48.5, 95.2)	494	1.66 (0.81, 3.33)	80.9 (55.7, 96.4)
4	Natsal 4-week	14 days	0.80 (0.36, 1.56)	55.1 (30.3, 79.0)	772	0.93 (0.43, 2.01)	60.5 (34.7, 86.6)

^a CrI: credible interval.

Figure S4. ABC-PMMH trace plot and the posterior distribution of β for scenario 1 (main analysis). We assumed the sexual partner distribution based on the reported 4-week number and infectious period of 10 days (main analysis).

Figure S5. ABC-PMMH trace plot and the posterior distribution of β for scenario 2. We assumed the sexual partner distribution based on the reported 1-year number and infectious period of 10 days.

Figure S6. ABC-PMMH trace plot and the posterior distribution of β for scenario 3. We assumed the sexual partner distribution based on the reported 4-week number and infectious period of 7 days.

Figure S7. ABC-PMMH trace plot and the posterior distribution of β for scenario 4. We assumed the sexual partner distribution based on the reported 4-week number and infectious period of 14 days.

Figure S8. Projected outcomes from the international spread model for four scenarios. (A) The simulated importation probabilities conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea (hatched bars). Double asterisks (**) beside country/territory names indicate ≥ 1 importation known to be from other Asian countries and territories and a single asterisk (*) indicates ≥ 1 importation but not known to be from Asia. (B) Distribution of the final outbreak sizes in Asia among the simulations, defined as the total number of cases over all the Asian countries and territories included until the end of simulations. (C) Distribution of the number of countries and territories with ≥ 1 importation. IP: infectious period.

Figure S9. Simulated and observed first importation dates. The simulated (bars) and observed (red circles) first importation dates since 2023 for mpox in Asia by date of reporting. Observed first importation dates were restricted to those reported by the end of 2024. Simulated importation dates were assumed to be lagged 12 days from the dates of infection reflecting reporting delay. The

simulations were run on 16 January 2023 onward. The horizontal bars and the vertical lines in their middle represent 90% simulation ranges and the medians for the first importation dates, conditional on the existence of any importation. Different bar colours distinguish between countries and countries with (blue) and without (light blue) ≥ 1 observed importation in the real world as of 2024 year-end. Double asterisks (**) beside country/territory names indicate ≥ 1 importation known to be from other Asian countries and territories, and a single asterisk (*) indicates ≥ 1 importation but not known to be from Asia. IP: infectious period.

Sensitivity analysis 2: different conditioning on the international spread

We varied the conditionals on the international spread we used in model fitting. In the main analysis, we conditioned the posterior distribution such that there were at least 10 cases in South Korea in the simulations by the end of the fitting period. Instead, we applied three alternative conditions: (i) unconditional (model fitted solely based on incidence in Japan); (ii) conditional to ≥ 10 cases in Taiwan; and (iii) conditional to ≥ 10 cases in mainland China (Figure S10).

Figure S10. Projected outcomes from the international spread model for different conditions. (A) The simulated importation probabilities for alternative conditionals. Hatched bars represent the country/territory on which the estimation was conditioned (to have ≥ 10 cases). Double asterisks (**) beside country/territory names indicate ≥ 1 importation known to be from other Asian countries and territories and a single asterisk (*) indicates ≥ 1 importation but not known to be from Asia. (B) Distribution of the final outbreak sizes in Asia among the simulations, defined as the total number of cases over all the Asian countries and territories included until the end of simulations. (C) Distribution of the number of countries and territories with ≥ 1 importation. IP: infectious period.

Sensitivity analysis 3: assortative mixing

In our transmission model, we assumed that the sexual contact network follows proportionate mixing,³⁵ i.e. a pair of individuals with sexual activity levels k and l are connected with a probability that is proportional to the product of their partnership rates ($r_k r_l$). This assumption is a commonly accepted simplification for heterogeneous transmission models but neglects the degree assortativity observed for MSM partnerships.^{36,37} Chow et al.³⁶ reported that 180 among 610 pairs (29.5%) of male-to-male partners visiting a sexual clinic in Australia on the same day were monogamous partnerships (i.e. both reporting only one partner over the last 3 months) and that the Newman's assortativity coefficient³⁸ was 0.264 (95% CI: 0.218–0.309). We rearranged our proportionate mixing network by increasing monogamous partnerships to mimic such an assortative network. Namely, we assumed that 55.3% of individuals whose partnership rate r_k is smaller than $2/90$ (i.e. less than 2 partners over 3 months) in our model formed monogamous partnerships within themselves such that those partnerships account for 29.5% of the total partnerships in the network. This resulted in partnerships originally connected to those (now-)monogamous individuals being cut; these connections were then rewired to individuals outside of the monogamous groups according to proportionate mixing. After this rewiring, the Newman's assortativity coefficient increased from 0.0 to 0.256, which is similar to the value reported by Chow et al.³⁶ We recalibrated this model with increased assortativity to the mpox incidence in Japan and simulated international spread.

The estimated conditional SAR was 71.6% (95% credible interval: 44.2, 91.7), which is comparable to the estimates in the main analysis. The projection results were similar to the main analysis (Figure S11).

Figure S11. Projected outcomes from the international spread model with the increased degree assortativity. (A) The simulated importation probabilities conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea (hatched bars). Double asterisks (**) beside country/territory names indicate ≥ 1 importation known to be from other Asian countries and territories, and a single asterisk (*) indicates ≥ 1 importation but not known to be from Asia. (B) Distribution of the final outbreak sizes in Asia among the simulations, defined as the total number of cases over all the Asian countries and territories included until the end of simulations. (C) Distribution of the number of countries and territories with ≥ 1 importation. IP: infectious period.

Sensitivity analysis 4: maximum number of sexual partners

In our model, the number of annual partners for the highest sexual activity group was 9,041. However, in the main analysis using finite and integer population sizes, individuals were only present up to the third-highest sexual activity group (corresponding to 6,259 annual partners) due to extremely low frequencies of the highest sexual activity groups (e.g. approximately $\sim 10^{-8}$) in the Weibull distribution fitted to the Natsal data. Regardless, it is unclear whether these are realistic numbers given the absence of datasets on MSM partnerships with a sufficiently large sample size. To assess the influence of assuming such a large upper limit, we instead used a distribution truncated at 1,000 sexual partners per year. We recalibrated this model with a lower upper limit to the mpoX incidence in Japan for simulation.

The estimated conditional SAR was 70.4% (95% credible interval: 47.5, 93.6), which is comparable to the estimates in the main analysis. Projected simulated importation probabilities (Figure S12A) also exhibited a similar trend to the main analysis (Figure S8), though slightly higher simulated importation probabilities were observed for countries deemed low-risk.

Figure S12. Projected outcomes from the international spread model in which the estimated sexual partner distribution per year was capped at 1,000. (A) The simulated importation probabilities conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea (hatched bars). Double asterisks (**) beside country/territory names indicate ≥ 1 importation known to be from other Asian countries and territories, and a single asterisk (*) indicates ≥ 1 importation but not known to be from Asia. (B) Distribution of the final outbreak sizes in Asia among the simulations, defined as the total number of cases over all the Asian countries and territories included until the end of simulations. (C) Distribution of the number of countries and territories with ≥ 1 importation. IP: infectious period.

Sensitivity analysis 5: behavioural change in Japan

We did not consider behavioural changes in Japan in the main analysis since there has been no documentation of sexual behaviour changes among the MSM population during the mpox outbreak in Japan in 2023. However, several Japanese community-based organisations were engaged in mpox-related public communication for MSM in April 2023 in response to the growing number of mpox cases.^{39–41} If these community actions had induced substantial behavioural changes, our main analysis might have underestimated the transmissibility of mpox due to an unmodelled reduction in contact rates in the later part of the incidence data (i.e. between mid-April and 16th June 2023). As a sensitivity analysis to account for this, we re-calibrated our model only using the mpox incidence data in Japan up to mid-April, which we assume was less affected by behavioural changes, if any. With this estimate, we conducted a counterfactual projection in Japan and other Asian countries and territories from 2023 onwards in the absence of any behavioural changes.

The posterior samples were conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea until 26 June 2023 to be comparable to the main analysis, yielding the conditional SAR estimates of 90.5% (95% credible interval: 55.7, 97.8). Our projected mpox incidence in Japan was higher than the main analysis regardless of conditioning on the importation in South Korea (Figure S13A&B). Both simulated importation probability and final outbreak size were higher than the main analysis, but the order of simulated importation probabilities between countries and territories remained consistent with the main analysis (Figure S14).

Figure S13: Counterfactual projection of mpox incidence in Japan from posterior samples, given the behavioural change was assumed not to happen from mid-April 2023. (A) The simulated trajectories of mpox incidence from the posterior samples conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea. The shaded area represents the fitting period from 16th January to mid-April 2023. (B) The simulated trajectories of mpox incidence from unconditional posterior samples.

Figure S14: Counterfactual outcomes from the international spread model given the behavioural change was assumed not to happen from mid-April 2023. (A) The simulated importation probabilities conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea (hatched bars). Double asterisks (**) beside country/territory names indicate ≥ 1 importation known to be from other Asian countries and territories, and a single asterisk (*) indicates ≥ 1 importation but not known to be from Asia. (B) Distribution of the final outbreak sizes in Asia among the simulations, defined as the total number of cases over all the Asian countries and territories included until the end of simulations. (C) Distribution of the number of countries and territories with ≥ 1 importation. IP: infectious period.

Sensitivity analysis 6: estimated international travel volume in 2023

We used the 2019 UNWTO international travel volume data since their 2023 data was unavailable at the time of analysis. To estimate the 2023 travel volume from country/territory i to j (M_{ij}), we adjusted the 2019 travel volume by multiplying the ratios of the flight passenger volume between the two countries in 2019 and 2023 ($h_{ij,flight}$). These ratios were calculated using the OAG flight dataset.⁴²

The histogram and heatmap of $h_{ij,flight}$ indicated the international flight volume in 2023 was generally comparable to 2019, although with a slight decline as a whole (a geometric mean of 0.90-fold) (Figure S15). For some country/territory pairs with small flight passenger volumes, $h_{ij,flight}$ took extremely large or small values. These extreme $h_{ij,flight}$ values that fell outside the 5th and 95th percentiles (0.28 and 3.68, respectively) were truncated to these bounds; these extreme values were only found for country pairs with less than 10,000 annual passengers. We assumed $h_{ij,flight}$ for country/territory pairs with missing OAG flight passenger data while M_{ij} for 2023 was then estimated as $M_{ij}^{2023} = h_{ij,flight}M_{ij}^{2019}$.

The simulated importation probabilities using the estimated 2023 international travel volume decreased by 10% to 20% from the main analysis for most countries and territories but the overall trend remained similar (Figure S16).

Figure S15: Ratios of the OAG flight passenger volume for each country/territory pair between 2019 and 2023 in (A) histogram and (B) heatmap. Blank areas in the heatmap represent missing values in either of the OAG flight passenger volumes in 2019 or 2023.

Figure S16: Projected outcomes from the international spread model where the 2019 UNWTO international travel volume was adjusted to 2023 using the ratio of the OAG flight volume data between 2019 and 2023. (A) The simulated importation probabilities conditioned on ≥ 10 cases in South Korea (hatched bars). Double asterisks () beside country/territory names indicate ≥ 1 importation known to be from other Asian countries and territories, and a single asterisk (*) indicates ≥ 1 importation but not known to be from Asia. (B) Distribution of the final outbreak sizes in Asia among the simulations, defined as the total number of cases over all the Asian countries and territories included until the end of simulations. (C) Distribution of the number of countries and territories with ≥ 1 importation. IP: infectious period.**

Comparison of the sexual partnership distribution between the UK and Japan

To assess the plausibility of the assumption that the sexual partnership distributions in all considered countries and territories are sufficiently similar to the empirical data from the UK Natsal,³ we compared the 1-year partner distributions between Natsal and the National Inventory of Japanese Sexual Behavior (NInJaS) collected in Japan.⁴³ Comparisons with other Asian countries and territories are included in the next section.

The sexual partnership distribution among MSM used in our model based on the UK Natsal data³ was derived from the reported number of sexual partners among men aged 18-44 who reported at least one same-sex sexual partner over a year. The exactly comparable data was not available in the NInJaS data, which collected the number of sexual partners in the last 12 months among men aged 20-39 reporting having sex with men in their lifetime but without exactly specifying the gender of partners. That is, the participants in NInJaS reported the number of overall sexual partners over 12 months and whether these partners were, as a whole, (i) all opposite-sex, (ii) mostly opposite-sex, (iii) half-and-half, (iv) mostly same-sex or (v) all same-sex. We attempted to infer the distribution of the number of same-sex partners among MSM in the NInJaS data by assigning weights to the reported number of partners according to the reported breakdown of gender (i)–(v); i.e. when a participant reported n_p sexual partners in the previous year, we assumed that the following fraction p_M among these partners was male: (i): $p_M = 0$; (ii): $p_M = \psi$; (iii): $p_M = 0.5$; with a response (iv): $p_M = 1 - \psi$; (v): $p_M = 1$. We then used $n_{MSM} = p_M n_p$ as the number of male sexual partners among MSM. We generally allowed n_{MSM} to be non-integer for convenience. However, for comparability with the Natsal data, from which we only included individuals with one or more male sexual partners, we substituted n_{MSM} 's that are smaller than 1 with 1's but with a sample weight of n_{MSM} (e.g. a sample of $n_{MSM} = 0.1$ was considered as a sample with one partner and a sample weight of 0.1).

We compared the sexual partner distributions from the Natsal and the NInJaS with $\psi=0.05, 0.2, 0.4$ (Figure S17). Overall, the distributions from NInJaS data showed a similar trend to the Natsal data.

Figure S17. The complementary cumulative distribution function for the 1-year sexual partnership distribution for the Natsal and NInJaS datasets. The parameter ψ represents the assumed proportion of males among the reported sexual partners when the respondents indicated their partners were mostly opposite-sex / same-sex.

Comparison of the sexual partnership distribution between the UK and Asian countries and territories

We also compared our modelled partnership distributions based on the UK Natsal data with the Asian Internet MSM Sex Survey (AIMSS), a large online survey on MSM across 24 Asian countries/territories including 13,883 participants.^{44,45} Following the MSM definition in AIMSS,^{44,46} we included participants meeting the following three criteria: i) assigned male at birth, ii) aged 18 years old or above and iii) had had at least one male sex partner in the previous six months. After excluding participants with inconsistent responses, we included 10,317 participants in the analysis. The distribution for total participants (from 24 countries/territories) and distributions for 12 Asian countries/territories with more than 100 participants were obtained.

Unlike the Natsal, specifying the exact number of partners for each participant, the AIMSS only collected the partner numbers in bins (1, 2–5, 6–10, 11–50 and 51+). In addition, different time windows were used for reporting partners between the Natsal (4-week or 1-year) and the AIMSS (half-year). To account for these differences, instead of directly comparing the Natsal original data points, we compared the AIMSS data with the Weibull distributions fitted to the 4-week and 1-year partnership data from the Natsal,^{3,4} i.e. the partnership distributions we used in our model. We linearly rescaled these Weibull distributions to represent half-year partnerships, calculated the areas under the curve corresponding to AIMSS bins (i.e. [1,2), [2,6), [6,11), [11,51), [51,∞)) and normalised them to yield categorical distributions.

We used two types of comparison, where we either included or excluded those reporting no more than one partner. This is because the above process of rescaling and binning the Weibull distributions along with the different definitions for MSM (having at least one male-to-male partner over 6 months vs 1 year) can introduce uncertainty in the proportion of individuals with small numbers of partners. For example, an individual with two partners in the last year was assumed to have had one partner over the last 6 months in the rescaling process; however in reality such an individual may have had two partners more than 6 months ago and none within the last 6 months, and thus may not qualify as MSM as per AIMSS's criteria. Such issues are likely less impactful for the bins of two or more partners over 6 months (i.e. four or more over 1 year). Although we could not fully validate the similarity in the proportion of individuals with less than two partners over 6 months between the Natsal and AIMSS, those individuals would have minimal impact on the transmission dynamics in our model as their partnership rate over the infectious period of mpox (i.e. 10 days in our model) would be negligibly small.

The proportions of individuals with only one male partner over 6 months in the modelled Natsal distributions were larger than those in the AIMSS, possibly because of the above limitation (Figure S18A). However, when this bin was excluded, the distributions were overall similar, including countries where homosexuality is criminalised⁴⁷ (Figure S18B).

Figure S18. The distributions of the 6-month male sexual partnership distribution among MSM for Asian countries and territories from the AIMSS and the UK from the Natsal. (A) The distribution of male-to-male sexual partnerships including men reporting only one sexual partner. The “All” represents all participants from 24 Asian countries/territories included in the AIMSS. The distributions for named Asian countries/territories are also from the AIMSS. The estimated sexual partnership distributions used in our model were rescaled to a half-year rate to obtain the Natsal 4-week (modelled) and 1-year (modelled) distributions. Whiskers represent confidence intervals based on the Quesenberry-Hurst method.⁴⁸ (B) The distribution of male sexual partnerships excluding men reporting only one sexual partner.

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